

Analysis of the EGPRS Lead-Cooled Fast Reactor Benchmark with WIMS and MONK®

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ABSTRACT

The Lead-Cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) concept has been identified as a promising candidate for the advanced Generation IV reactor system due to its desirable nuclear properties and high level of passive safety. The lack of operative experience of LFRs in the civil space leaves a gap in the industry knowledge required to support design, verification and licensing of these reactors. Development and construction of demonstrator reactors are planned by a number of European organisations. To support this, the EGPRS Benchmark – based on the planned ALFRED design – has been established with the intent to develop industry understanding of modern LFR physics, and to provide a validation route for neutronic codes and methods for the LFR system.

The ANSWERS codes WIMS (deterministic reactor physics) and MONK (Monte Carlo criticality and reactor physics) are applied to phases I and II of the EGPRS LFR benchmark using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 data library. Good agreement between the two codes is observed for integral parameters and cross sections across the fuel pin, fuel assembly and control rod and shield supercell configurations. A subset of the benchmark results are presented, along with initial results for the Phase III BOC whole core.

Keywords: Lead-Cooled Fast Reactor, ALFRED, WIMS, Deterministic, Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

The EGPRS Lead-Cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) benchmark is based on the Advanced LFR European Demonstrator (ALFRED) design. The programme consists of three phases of modelling:

- Single fuel pincell
- Fuel subassembly and control rod/reflector supercells
- Whole core

The phases target a range of in-core environments, capturing key spectral and interaction phenomena between fuel, structural and absorber components. At each stage, generation of integral parameters, cross section and flux data are mandated. This paper documents the initial modelling performed with deterministic reactor physics code WIMS [4], with comparisons to Monte Carlo reactor physics code MONK® [2] to serve as a method of comparison and validation.

1.1. Benchmark Description

The ALFRED core concept is a 300 MWth lead-cooled fast reactor [1]. Figure 1 shows the radial schematic of the fuelled region, highlighting the main subassembly types. The core is composed of 253 subassemblies:

- 56 inner Fuel Assemblies (FAs)
- 78 outer Fuel Assemblies (FAs)
- 12 Control Rods (CRs)
- 4 Safety Devices (SDs)
- 1 Test Assembly (TA)
- 48 Reflector Assemblies (RAs)
- 54 Shield Assemblies (SAs)

The fuel is loaded in stacks of sintered hypo-stoichiometric mixed U+Pu oxide (MOX) fuel pellets, with two distinct regions; inner fuel at 20.5 wt.% PuO₂, and outer fuel composed of 26.2 wt.% PuO₂.

Figure 1. Radial configuration of the ALFRED core fuelled region – Source: ALFRED specifications of the OECD/NEA LFR benchmark.

1.2. Code Description

Both WIMS and MONK are codes developed by the Amentum ANSWERS® Software Service, based in Dorset, UK.

The WIMS code is a flexible deterministic modular multigroup code, capable of modelling many spectrum and geometry classes. WIMS has a long pedigree within the UK and international nuclear industry and employs a range of flux solution methods including collision probabilities, diffusion, SP3 and transport theory. The resonance shielding calculation can employ a mix of equivalence and subgroup theory methods for thermal and intermediate systems, and methods targeted to the treatment of the heterogeneity and streaming effects for a fast spectrum system.

MONK is a Monte Carlo code developed for criticality and reactor physics analyses and is an industry standard for criticality and reactor physics analyses in the UK.

Both WIMS and MONK use bespoke data libraries produced by ANSWERS, with versions based on all the major international evaluations including JEFF and ENDF/B. The standard WIMS multigroup library is tabulated in the XMAS 172 group scheme, with supplemental libraries in 1968 groups for fast spectrum calculations. MONK leverages continuous energy libraries for the BINGO collision processor. In the case of this analysis, library ENDF/B-VIII.0 is used.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. WIMS

As a modular code, the calculation in WIMS is performed in a set of discrete steps. First, cross section generation for fast spectrum systems is performed with the WIMSECCO module, an embedded implementation of the European Cell Code (ECCO) [5]. WIMSECCO prepares self-shielded cross sections by solving the slowing down equations in a detailed 1968 energy group scheme, with the subgroup method for the intra-group calculation. The heterogeneous assembly flux is calculated using the collision probability method, which is used to condense the material cross sections into the standard WIMS XMAS 172 energy group scheme. This process is used to generate sets of material cross sections for each of the fuel assembly, control rod assembly and shield assembly lattices. Cross sections for the

non-fissile subcritical lattices (control and shield) are generated in WIMSECCO by applying a source spectrum derived from a homogeneous representation of the fuel lattice.

The material cross sections are combined into a heterogeneous geometry for each benchmark phase, and a transport solution is performed with the method of characteristics module CACTUS to produce a detailed flux and k-infinity solution in 172 groups [1].

Cross section data is extracted via Python scripts using the FCP (Fortran-C-Python) functionality, which exposes calculational data to the user via a Python dictionary for convenient postprocessing.

For the Phase III whole core calculations, the WIMS core model used is a smeared-assembly geometry on a regular triangular grid. For the fuel subassemblies, homogenised cross sections are obtained by flux-volume smearing the heterogeneous transport model (Figure 4). Cross sections for non-fissile structural materials are calculated with WIMSECCO using the homogenised fuel assembly source method described above. For the strongly absorbing control rod and safety device subassembly cross sections, the SPH (Super - Homogenisation) method is used, which uses the fluxes derived from the Phase II supercells (Figure 5) in an iterative scheme to converge upon a corrected set of homogeneous cross sections. A 2D RZ core model is used to generate a 172-group flux spectrum for condensation and homogenisation to 33 groups for the 3D core solve.

A development version of the WIMS11C code is used for these calculations.

2.2. MONK

Monte Carlo reactor physics and criticality code MONK is used for comparison against the WIMS results, using the continuous energy implementation of the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data evaluation. Calculations are run to a specified stochastic uncertainty of the K_{eff} estimator in a set of discrete stages. At each stage, MONK tracks a specified number of particle superhistories (default 10), where each superhistory includes the full transport and fission progeny for a set number of fission generations until absorption or leakage. Before the tracking stages are performed, 10 initial settling stages are run to converge the fission source, which do not contribute to the final statistics. Confidence in the fission source convergence can be obtained by examining the evolution of the Shannon entropy. For all phases the calculations are run to a statistical uncertainty of 1 pcm on K_{eff} .

The model geometry is built using the Fractal Geometry package, which allows the detailed heterogeneous geometry to be fully represented. Although not used in this benchmark, additional geometric complexity can be modelled using the Hole geometry package, which employs woodcock delta tracking.

A development version of the MONK12C is used for these calculations

3. RESULTS

3.1. Phase I

The first benchmark phase is the analysis of a single reflected pincell.

Figure 2 shows the full plan MONK model and the one-sixth plan WIMS model in CACTUS. Both inner (FINN) and outer (FOUT) fuel models are considered. Table 1 compares the k-infinity for the two cases.

Figure 2. Left: full plan MONK geometry. Right: one-sixth WIMS geometry.

Table 1. Pincell k -infinity.

	FINN	FOUT
MONK (± 1 pcm)	1.35685	1.54330
WIMS	1.35543	1.54301
dk (pcm)	142	29

Figure 3. Left: comparison of the pincell neutron flux calculated by the two codes. Right: percentage difference (WIMS-MONK).

Figure 3 shows a comparison of the total system flux calculated by the two codes. Very good agreement is seen across the much of the energy spectrum. At lower energy ranges below ~ 100 eV, and energies greater than 10 MeV WIMS begins to deviate from MONK, which is most significantly due to the increased stochastic uncertainty of the MONK calculation in energy groups where neutron population is low. Stochastic uncertainty on the flux remains under 1 % in the range ~ 100 eV – 10.0 MeV.

Table 2 lists the percentage difference between selected microscopic cross sections calculated by the two codes.

Table 2. FINN pincell microscopic cross section percentage difference, MONK-WIMS.

Nuclide	Capture	Fission	Elastic Scatter	Inelastic Scatter
Pb204	-0.63	-	0.05	-0.34
Pb206	1.05	-	0.17	-0.36
Pb207	-0.07	-	-1.39	-0.29
Pb208	3.41	-	5.16	-0.78
Fe	0.34	-	0.15	0.06
U235	-0.09	-0.24	0.01	-0.04
U238	0.24	-0.43	0.49	0.02
Pu239	-0.26	-0.03	0.01	0.06
Pu241	-0.90	-0.29	-0.04	0.01

Excellent agreement is seen across the major nuclides and reactions. The only notable outliers are Pb208 capture and elastic scatter.

3.2. Phase II-a

Figure 4. Left: full plan MONK geometry. Right: one-sixth WIMS geometry.

Phase II-a concerns an infinitely reflected fuel subassembly. Figure 4 shows the WIMS and MONK models used.

Table 3. FINN fuel assembly microscopic cross section percentage difference, MONK-WIMS.

Nuclide	Capture	Fission	Elastic Scatter	Inelastic Scatter
Pb204	-0.58	-	0.06	-0.53
Pb206	0.99	-	0.15	-0.51
Pb207	-0.03	-	-1.33	-0.61
Pb208	2.79	-	5.07	-0.41
Fe	-0.30	-	-0.86	0.32
U235	0.01	-0.05	0.04	-0.17
U238	-0.07	-0.52	0.32	-0.19
Pu239	0.17	0.05	0.07	-0.06
Pu241	-0.69	-0.07	-0.01	-0.17

Table 4. Fuel subassembly k -infinity.

	FINN	FOUT
MONK (± 1 pcm)	1.28773	1.46984
WIMS	1.28767	1.47108
dk (pcm)	-5	124

Agreement here is very good, with the Pb208 capture and elastic scatter overestimation trend mirroring that of the pincell case.

3.3. Phase II-b

Figure 5. One-sixth supercell geometry used in MONK and WIMS. The outer region within the triangular prism is filled with void material, with a reflective boundary condition. Left: Control rod supercell. Right: Shield assembly supercell.

Phase II-b concerns the modelling of a supercell of one ring of fuel subassemblies surrounding a central control rod subassembly, with macroscopic cross sections reported in the 7-group scheme shown in Table 5. Figure 5 shows the one-sixth rotational geometry used in both WIMS and MONK.

Table 5. Homogeneous control rod supercell macroscopic cross section percentage differences, MONK-WIMS.

Group	Upper bound (MeV)	Capture	Fission
1	1.96403E+01	-1.58	-4.99
2	2.23130E+00	-1.95	-4.22
3	4.97871E-01	-4.24	-3.93
4	6.73795E-02	-3.52	-4.50
5	2.03468E-03	-3.67	-2.68
6	2.26033E-05	-2.73	2.32
7	5.40000E-07	-75.27	-78.62

Table 6. Control rod supercell k -infinity

	FINN	FOUT
MONK (± 1 pcm)	0.78181	0.91960
WIMS	0.78216	0.92122
dk (pcm)	35	162

Excellent agreement is seen for the supercell k_{inf} , demonstrating effective capture of the physics of the heterogeneous high-flux gradient on the fuel-control rod boundary. Homogenised supercell macroscopic cross sections show good agreement, with the exception of the lower thermal groups, which show a significant discrepancy due to the stochastic noise on the Monte Carlo flux and reaction rates. This is most likely due to the naturally low thermal neutron population of the fast reactor, exacerbated by the presence of the B₄C control rods, and the highly thermal boundary of group 7.

3.4. Phase II-c

Phase II-c concerns the same supercell layout as II-b, but with the control rod subassembly in the centre replaced with a shield assembly. The shield assembly (SA) takes the same geometry as the fuel subassembly, but with the fuel pins replaced with solid YSZ (Yttria-Stabilised Zirconia) reflective pellets; these are positioned around the edge of the full core, acting as reflectors. Figure 5 (right) shows the one-sixth rotational geometry used in WIMS and MONK.

Table 7. Shield assembly supercell k -infinity.

	FINN	FOUT
MONK (± 1 pcm)	1.17599	1.34495
WIMS	1.17607	1.34568
dk (pcm)	8	73

Table 8. Shield assembly supercell macroscopic cross section percentage differences, MONK-WIMS.

Group	Upper bound (MeV)	Capture	Fission
1	1.96403E+01	-5.36	-4.03
2	2.23130E+00	-3.86	-3.64
3	4.97871E-01	-3.71	-3.77
4	6.73795E-02	-3.77	-3.68
5	2.03468E-03	-4.37	-3.12
6	2.26033E-05	-1.02	0.66
7	5.40000E-07	-7.19	9.48

Excellent agreement is seen between the two codes for the supercell k_{inf} , with the cross sections generally well-captured. For both Phase II-b and II-c WIMS shows a ~ 2 -5% underprediction across both reactions which is not seen in the Phase II-a infinite fuel lattice case. This may justify further investigation into sensitivity of the calculation to the method of characteristics tracking parameters, given the increased heterogeneity of the problem. Agreement in thermal group 7 is much better than in Phase IIb, supporting the hypothesis that it is the control rods that are affecting the flux in this group. Further work to include acceleration techniques, such as splitting, could improve the statistics for these two phases and increase confidence in the deterministic results in this energy region.

3.5. Phase III

Phase III concerns the analysis of the full core. The WIMS model is constructed on a triangular mesh in the MERLIN diffusion/SP3 solver module. Preliminary results are presented for the BOC fresh fuel core.

Figure 6. Left: a slice through the heterogeneous full core geometry used in MONK. Middle: whole core geometry used in MERLIN. Right: homogeneous subassembly group MONK geometry.

 Table 9. Preliminary whole core k -effectives at BOC.

	K_{eff}	dk (pcm)
MONK (± 10 pcm)	1.04992	
WIMS (MERLIN SP3)	1.05548	556
WIMS (GROUP MONK, ± 10 pcm)	1.05022	31

For the fresh fuel beginning of cycle (BOC) configuration, the safety devices are fully withdrawn, with the control rods partially inserted in the lower part of the fuelled region. Two WIMS flux solvers are compared: the MERLIN SP3 solver and the MONK multigroup Monte Carlo solver (so called group MONK), both in the standard ECCO 33 group scheme. [3]

The MERLIN configuration comprises homogenised materials mapped onto a regular triangular lattice at a resolution of six triangles per hex. Further triangular subdivision of the mesh for flux solution is available but not used. Axially, the model comprises 40 material slices, subdivided into 152 sub-meshes in total for improved fidelity in the flux solution.

The group MONK solver is an implementation of the MONK code within WIMS, which can perform a Monte Carlo flux solution using the same homogeneous resonance shielded materials as the deterministic flux calculation. This allows for a direct comparison of solver methodology.

Good integral agreement is seen between the continuous energy and multigroup MC methods, supporting the applicability of the WIMS deterministic methods to core-level cross sections for LFR core. Agreement for the SP3 calculation is approaching acceptable with the same cross sections, however the level of discrepancy indicates that the SP3 method may not be appropriate for the LFR core flux solve. Further work is required to examine modelling sensitivities such as geometry resolution and meshing, to determine its applicability, with further comparison against a full transport calculation using the CACTUSOT method of characteristics solver to identify the most appropriate deterministic flux solution method at the full core level.

4. CONCLUSION

The deterministic cross section generation and flux solution methods within WIMS show very good applicability to the LFR core components at the varied length scales examined.

Excellent agreement is seen for the K_{inf} results for phases I and II of benchmark. The values for all WIMS cases in these phases are within 200 pcm dk of the MONK results. Excellent agreement is also seen for the 1-group microscopic cross sections for the pincell and fuel subassembly models. The 7-group macroscopic cross sections show good agreement, with WIMS generally exhibiting a ~2-5% underprediction compared to MONK for most energy groups. Further investigation into the sensitivity of these results to geometric and solver parameters is warranted, in order to improve agreement. Poor agreement is seen in the particularly thermal 7th group, for which a low neutron flux population leads to a high statistical uncertainty in the Monte Carlo calculation.

Further development and comparison of the phase III full core model is planned, with a full transport calculation expected to support the identification of the most appropriate flux solution method for the LFR full core.

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